

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ENDODONTIC PERIAPICAL LESION: AN OVERVIEW ON THE ETIOLOGY, DIAGNOSIS AND CURRENT TREATMENT MODALITIES

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Abstract

Chronic periapical periodontitis (CAP) is a typical oral disease in which periodontal inflammation caused by an odontogenic infection eventually leads to bone loss. Despite substantial progresses of modern endodontics with regards to mechanical instrumentation of radicular spaces, root canal infections, and their associated apical periodontitis lesions remain remarkably prevalent. Knowledge of microbial location, organisation and virulence factors within the root canal system is important for understanding the disease process.

Keywords: chronic apical periodontitis, microorganism; nonsurgical endodontic treatment, bone regeneration.

Introduction. Apical periodontitis (AP) is one of the most prevalent inflammatory lesions involving the jaw. A recent systematic review revealed that 52 % of the worldwide population and 50 % of the global adult population has at least one tooth with AP, and that the prevalence of AP is much higher among root-filled teeth (39 %) than among nontreated teeth (3 %) [1, 2].

Chronic apical periodontitis refers to the chronic inflammation of periapical tissues due to the long-term presence of infection and pathogenic irritants in the root canal, which is manifested by the formation of inflammation and destruction of alveolar bone. Evidence has reinforced the microbial role in apical periodontitis; AP is essentially an inflammatory disease of microbial aetiology [3].

Microbiota are found in highly organised and complex entities, known as multi-species biofilms mainly located inside the root canal. In specific circumstances, microorganisms can overcome the defence barrier and even establish an extra-radicular infection [4, 5]. Although fungi, archaea and viruses have been found in association with AP, bacteria are the main microbial aetiological agents [3].

It is known that microbial antigens from the root canal infection are capable to stimulate both specific and non-specific immune responses in periapical tissue [6, 7]. This inflammation is characterized by a complex interplay between microbial tissue invasion and host defense [8]. The defense mechanism keeps the microbial infection in the root canal system, thereby preventing its spread beyond the apical foramen, but the permanence of bacteria in the pulpal tissues leads to pulpal pathology and periapical inflammation [9].

The main text.

Etiologic role of microorganisms in developing of apical periodontitis

In 1894 W.D. Miller was the first who published observations from the root canals with infected pulp

space, but at that time he was unable to verify his findings [10]. Since that time bacteria was implicated in infections of endodontic origin. In 1982 Fabricius et al. showed the succession of strict anaerobes over facultative anaerobes with time in the root canal, which most likely occurred due to the changes in ecology of root canal system [11, 12].

Precise identification of microorganisms participating in the pathogenesis of apical periodontitis is important in order to understand the disease process and to provide effective antimicrobial treatment.

The oral cavity has one of the highest rates of microorganisms. Under appropriate conditions, the normal oral microbiota may give rise to opportunistic pathogens if access to dental pulp tissues occurs. The most common route of contamination is dental caries, inducing successive inflammatory responses in the pulp tissue, ending with pulp necrosis if appropriate therapeutic measures are not adopted [13, 14, 15]. The enclosed anatomy of the dental pulp provides an effective primary barrier against its microbial colonization, once the teeth are part of the oral cavity.

Microorganisms residing in the root canal play an essential role in the initiation and establishment of periradicular lesions [16]. Microorganisms may cause direct tissue damage and modulate the immunological response by secretion of products, including enzymes, exotoxins and metabolic end-products [17, 18, 19].

Current Challenges in the Diagnosis and Treatment of Apical Periodontitis

Since its inception, conventional radiography has remained the mainstay of imaging in Endodontics. Among the specific imaging techniques, which have been researched as potential diagnostic and treatment planning tools in Endodontics, are digital subtraction radiology (DSR), tuned aperture computed tomography (TACT), ultrasound (US), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and computed tomography (CT) [20, 21].

As such, conventional radiography, despite its inherent limitations (Compression of Three-Dimensional Structures, Geometric Distortion), remains the default imaging system in the field.

Cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) is a contemporary, three-dimensional, diagnostic imaging system designed specifically for use on the maxillofacial skeleton [22, 23]. A commonly used option is for the images of the area of interest to be displayed, simultaneously, in the three orthogonal planes (axial, sagittal and coronal), affording the clinician a truly three-dimensional view of the area of interest. Cone beam computed tomography overcomes the limitations of conventional radiography. The production of three-dimensional images allows a comprehensive appreciation of the anatomy, and its spatial relationship to the tissue destruction caused by the pathosis under examination. Cone beam computed tomography is significantly more sensitive than conventional radiography in the detection of apical periodontitis in humans [24]. Periapical bone destruction associated with endodontic infection can be identified using CBCT before evidence of the existence of these lesions presents itself on conventional radiographs [25, 26].

Challenges in the Treatment of Apical Periodontitis

Endodontic success has largely been based on three basic principles known as the "endodontic triad of success" which includes: cleaning (debridement and disinfection), shaping, and obturation (sealing) [27]. The goal of endodontic treatment is to clean, shape, and seal the root canal system in three dimensions to eliminate or prevent (re)infection. Treatment aims to remove or significantly reduce the intracanal microbes and prevent re-infection by placing a root canal filling. When endodontic treatment is adequately done, the periapical lesion heals with hard tissue regeneration, which is evident in follow-up radiographs through a reduction in the radiolucency's size [28].

Various clinical approaches involving nonsurgical endodontic treatment for the treatment of AP have been developed. Given the variability and complexity of the internal anatomy of teeth, which includes C-shaped root canals, curvatures, and lateral and apical ramifications, complete disinfection of contaminated root canals is difficult because of underlying pulp necrosis [29].

Irrigation, a key factor in the success of endodontic treatment, has several important functions depending on the irrigant used; these include destruction of the microorganisms in the root canal, dissolution of necrotic and inflamed tissue, removal of dentinal debris, prevention of bacterial extrusion into the periapical tissues, reduction of friction, improvement of the cutting effectiveness, and cooling of the endodontic file and tooth. Importantly, it affects areas of the root canal wall that are not accessible by mechanical instrumentation. Sodium hypochlorite, because of its specific ability to dissolve organic matter, is widely considered the primary irrigant of choice to effectively kill and remove bacteria and necrotic tissue remnants in the canal [1, 30, 31].

Antimicrobial therapy in endodontics has been established on the opinion that periradicular conditions are infectious entities. Such therapies should be able to eliminate pathogenic microorganisms; in this context, highly effective antimicrobial strategies should be applied to achieve optimal outcomes [32, 33].

Bone remodeling of AP

Bone remodeling is performed by altering bone resorption and formation in chronological order. Bone resorption and formation are opposing and coupled processes of osteoblasts and osteoclasts [34, 35], which together constitute normal bone mass. This section focuses on several factors that influence periapical bone remodeling, including microorganisms, human signaling pathways, and the immune system.

Conclusions.

The worldwide prevalence of apical periodontitis is high, and its treatment remains challenging. Improvement in endodontic instruments, instrumentation systems, irrigants, and ICM, along with the development of novel therapeutic approaches, are crucial for more effective procedures for treating infected root canals. Nonsurgical and surgical endodontic treatments have a high success rate in the treatment and prevention of apical periodontitis when carried out according to standard and accepted clinical principles.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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